

Open Scholarly Metadata in Action: A Joint Effort of Infrastructure and Publishing

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Purpose

At its core, the incremental nature of science is rooted in two embedded principles: (i) the integrity of its outputs and (ii) the permanence of its records within the information system. However, the true value of research records lies in the metadata providing the essential context for persistence to slow information entropy (Habermann 2020). As a trusted infrastructure provider, Crossref supports this framework by promoting open scholarly metadata through transparency, discoverability, and accountability, in alignment with the Barcelona Declaration and the overarching vision of the Research Nexus. In this context, Crossref emerges as a valuable bibliographic discovery tool, a role that has already been investigated in the arts and humanities (Borrego et al. 2023) though not yet from a holistic perspective.

In the shadowy areas of the reproducibility chain, metadata poses significant challenges, especially when stakeholders beyond infrastructure providers are involved. These challenges span analysis, reporting, storage, and preservation—a landscape that becomes even more intricate when regulatory factors come into play, ranging from federal to institutional recommendations and mandates (Margolis et al. 2014), all in pursuit of the overarching goal of establishing a sustainable research infrastructure aligned with the FAIR principles (Wilkinson et al. 2016; Bonino da Silva Santo et al 2023).

Among all stakeholders engaged in dialogue with Crossref to support this “awesome reproducible research” (Leipzig 2019), publishers stand at the forefront. This paper aims to explore the roles and responsibilities of publishers in ensuring metadata quality and its importance in maintaining the integrity and discoverability of scholarly records. Frontiers, an Open Access publisher, is used as a case study to examine best practices and collaborative efforts with Crossref and other key stakeholders in scholarly communication—an area that remains relatively underexplored in bibliography. This examination is particularly timely as publishers, leveraging their assessed infrastructure, are uniquely positioned to facilitate a “on-the-fly” FAIR future in research data management (Exner et al. 2023). By universally applying best practices across metadata systems, rather than confining them to specific disciplines or projects, publishers can help dismantle the ‘silo’ approach that currently limits the broader adoption of these standards.

Methods and expected outcome

Despite the ambiguity stemming from its etymological uncertainty, there is general agreement in defining metadata as the “glue” of reproducibility (Leipzig et al. 2021). Building on this, the analysis first shifts to the infrastructure perspective. Specifically, speakers highlight how Crossref ensures that metadata reliably reflects both the quality and context of scholarly works. Initiatives like the Integrity of Integrity of Scholarly Record (ISR) project, which is further amplified within the Principles of Open Scholarly Infrastructure (POSI) framework, provide the necessary context to explore a set of guidelines that empower metadata to address key questions: How can we better represent authorship and funding agencies behind research? How are datasets connected to publications? And how has the record evolved over time, whether through updates, corrections, or retractions?

Publisher’s role in this axis is then explored in detail. The second part of the presentation provides a quantitative snapshot of how leading publishers are performing in terms of metadata coverage and preservation. It identifies both the areas of strength and the “growth areas” of collaboration. These growth areas are examined in two ways: firstly, as limbo spaces where new collaboration frameworks can be developed, and secondly, as the most challenging areas that publishers face, both in terms of resource allocation and product-centric implementations.

To illustrate this, Frontiers serves as a lens to observe the win-win dynamic between publishers and infrastructure providers. The quantitative analysis therefore lays the foundation for a final, qualitative section that looks at potential future developments in the collaboration between publishers (e.g. Frontiers) and infrastructure providers (e.g. Crossref). In particular, a concluding section explores how such collaborations can further enhance open practices through (among others) strategic, metadata-focused plans.

A mixed-methods approach is used. The quantitative analysis draws on internal dashboards and public Crossref metadata records to assess key indicators of metadata completeness across publishers. The qualitative reflections are informed by expert exchanges, participation in metadata-focused working groups, and firsthand experience with implementation challenges at Frontiers. These insights are used to explore future opportunities for collaboration between publishers and infrastructure providers.

Results

The analysis revealed that achieving high-quality metadata involves a delicate balance between technological infrastructure and collaborative frameworks across stakeholders. Crossref’s role as a trusted infrastructure provider emerged as pivotal in ensuring metadata integrity, discoverability, and accountability. In the meantime, quantitative data on leading publishers highlighted significant strides in metadata coverage, with notable gaps in certain areas of collaboration. These “growth areas” are identified as both challenges and opportunities: while resource allocation and product-focused implementation remain hurdles, they also present spaces for innovative collaboration. Additionally, the findings underscore the expanding role of supplementary agents (i.e. funding bodies) in the scientometric landscape, necessitating more granular metadata schemes and reinforcing the dual responsibility of infrastructure agencies and publishers.

Value

As highlighted by the Metadata2020 initiative, achieving metadata quality at scale requires more than just technological infrastructure. It demands a collaborative, cross-stakeholder approach, ensuring that systems efforts align with practical implementation across publishing. Ensuring this continuity is vital for the sustained success and integrity of scholarly communication, with all involved parties working to ensure it.

Given this highly due preamble, the value of the present paper is to present publishers as privileged stakeholder invested of (i) a 'duty of care' to the published content, so that it remains discoverable, accessible, preservable and interoperable, (ii) a commitment to metadata stewardship, crucial for upholding the scholarly record's integrity and discoverability.

By effectively managing research metadata, publishers can a. escalate the quality of the publishing process, b. support any transparent agendas in the science ecosystem, and c. contribute to the overall advancement of knowledge dissemination. This paper aims to showcase the beneficial practices that drive publishers to generate comprehensive metadata for their content, ensuring its sharing, interlinking, and discoverability across platforms, while also addressing the implementation challenges faced by service providers like Crossref in enabling this ideal scenario for publishers.

In more details, the paper adopts a more narrowed approach in exploring roles, responsibilities, challenges and opportunities for an Open Access publisher in ensuring that the scholarly record is easy to find, cite, reuse and build upon thanks to the use of metadata. Speakers discuss how Frontiers works with Crossref – and Crossref with Frontiers – as well as other stakeholders in this space to better understand industry trends and user needs, thus asserting continued prominence in the Open Science debate. Among the lessons learned that help forecast future scenarios, the recent expansion of the scientometric landscape is further discussed (Fradkin, Mugnaini 2021). It triangulates the axis by including funding bodies: to what extent will these bodies increasingly require the recognition of their contributions, thereby placing greater responsibility on authors to acknowledge them, and on publishers/providers to refine existing metadata schemes?

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